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Using Digital Tools for Enhanced Student Learning and Engagement in Particle Technology Courses at Graz University of Technology

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Introduction

Digital-based approaches to enhance student learning and engagement have seen much attention during the past ten years. These approaches have included online learning management systems, MOOCs, student response feedback systems, among others. At Graz University of Technology (TU Graz), there has been a significant emphasis on using digital tools, which have been previously reported¹⁻². Digital tools and adaptive learning have posed a challenge to the academic community, in that new assessment methods and data analytics are necessary to quantitatively determine enhanced student learning and engagement. Both quantitative and qualitative approaches have been studied, though many are dependent on the learning habits and preferences of a particular student³.

At TU Graz, multiple digital tools were used to enhance the student learning and engagement in the Particle Technology sequence of courses. The three main tools that were used were: (i) Perusall, (ii) Feedbackr, and (iii) TeachCenter. The three primary goals in using these digital tools were (i) to enhance student learning, (ii) improve student engagement in the classroom, and (iii) to obtain rapid feedback regarding student understanding of the course materials.

Our present concept paper will highlight how these digital tools were introduced in the course sequence, as well as some best-practice recommendations for classroom and course implementation.

The Particle Technology sequence at TU Graz consists of two courses: Particle Technology I (a lecture), which primarily focuses on more introductory material, and Particle Technology II (a combined lecture and practical), which focuses on more advanced topics, such as gas-particle separation processes. All three digital tools were used in the Particle Technology sequence. The following section describes each digital tool in more detail.

1. Digital Tools

1.1 Perusall

Perusall is a digital platform that allows students to collaboratively annotate textbooks, papers, and other similar classroom reading assignments⁴. It is a web-based tool that allows for commenting on otherwise static content. Students can essentially “crowd source” comments, questions, and answers on text-based course materials using this digital platform. The students’ asynchronous responses, comments, questions are recorded (these records include student names and timestamps), and shown to the class and instructor. Additionally, if wanted, the student comments can be scored by a machine learning algorithm. Previous uses of Perusall in physics courses found that the students who engage in high-level discussion online make more gains in conceptual understanding than students who do not⁵. Another use of Perusall, in a chemical engineering course, found that at least 80-90% of the students believed it was a useful educational tool and that they learned new material by responding to other students’ comments⁶.

In order to introduce Perusall to the Particle Technology courses, five different papers were assigned to the classes to read as supplemental material⁷⁻¹¹. Although class attendance is not mandatory for these courses at TU Graz by law, the instructors decided to consider an outside-the-classroom method to help engage students in studying the material. The assigned papers brought additional depth and introduced contemporary concepts to the course material. Students were asked to provide approximately three annotations per paper.

Fig 1 shows an example of what a paper digitally highlighted in Perusall looks like. The yellow highlighted text has been annotated by students, either using comments or questions. These comments and questions are called a “conversation” in Perusall. It is essentially a thread of comments for a paper. Fig 2 shows a list of conversations for the material highlighted on page 1 of the paper (Fig 1). Fig 3 shows an example of a single conversation between two students and a particular topic found within the paper.

**Characterization of Lunar Dust for Toxicological Studies.
I: Particle Size Distribution**

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Abstract: The particle size distribution (PSD) of lunar dust, the <20 μm portion of the regolith, was determined as an initial step in the study of the possible toxicological effects it may have on the human respiratory and pulmonary systems. Utilizing scanning electron microscopy, PSDs were determined for Apollo 11 (10084) and 17 (70051) dust samples, as well as lunar dust simulant JSC-1Avf. The novel methodology employed is described in detail. All measured PSDs feature a log-normal distribution having a single mode in a range 100–300 nm for lunar dust samples, but the lunar simulant has a mode at ~600 nm.

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CE Database subject headings: Dust; Moon; Particle size; Toxicity.

Introduction

NASA has recently announced major space missions to return human beings to the Moon, and then to Mars, and beyond. Immediate plans are to use the Moon as a test bed for Mars and for a propellant fueling station, with the in situ resource utilization of lunar materials providing for the establishment of a permanent lunar outpost. Regolith and soil on the Moon will be used to construct a base, but also will be processed to produce oxygen and hydrogen for rocket fuel, and helium (³He) for possible nuclear energy (Taylor 1992a, b; Taylor and Carrier 1993; Taylor and Kulcinski 1999). All activities on the Moon, be they regolith handling and processing or simply moving on the lunar surface, have one factor in common—involvement with lunar dust, with its numerous deleterious effects. Lunar dust is the <20 μm portion of the lunar soil, makes up ~20% by weight, and consists mostly of sharp, irregular-shaped, abrasive, impact-produced glass. Because of the unique environment prevailing on the lunar surface, the soil and its dust contain myriads of nanophase metallic Fe particles that impart the soil with unexpected properties of ferromagnetism (Taylor et al. 2005) and extreme coupling to microwave energy (Taylor and Meek 2005).

During the Apollo missions, the astronauts experienced unanticipated problems due to the ubiquitous lunar dust. Many of the astronauts experienced problems including eye, nose, and throat irritation, to different degrees. With plans of returning humans to the Moon for prolonged stays (e.g., 15–90 days), it is imperative that the possible physiologic effects of lunar dust on respiratory systems be thoroughly investigated (Park et al. 2006a,b; Taylor et al. 2005). The detrimental and adverse effects of the lunar dust must be carefully examined. In particular, it is the <2 μm particles that can readily remain in human lungs, where they can cause fibrosis or even enter directly into the blood stream, particularly when <100 nm. As a first step in the understanding of lunar dust and its deleterious effects, studies have been undertaken on the particle size distribution (PSD) and morphology of some Apollo lunar dust samples.

After each Apollo mission, the various lunar soil samples collected had their PSDs determined by wet/dry sieving. Largely because of sieving limitations, such size distributions were measured primarily from millimeters down to 20 μm (Morris et al. 1983; Graf 1993). Several studies measured size distributions of lunar soil down to 1 μm (Duke et al. 1970; Heywood 1971; Carrier 1973; Butler et al. 1973; Butler and King 1974; McKay et al. 1974; Greene et al. 1975). However, the submicron grain sizes have not been well examined to date. One reason for the scarcity of submicron size data was their perceived lack of importance for lunar soil science (i.e., origin and evolution). Until now, the possible toxicology of lunar dust was not an important subject. In

Fig 1. Example of highlighted annotated text in Perusall.

? In my point of view its interesting that the authors are... 3

To my mind this could be avoided or at least minimized by a...

? How can the phsysiologic effects of lunar dust be tested ...

? **Is this similar to the effect of asbestos?** 3

? Do I have to be affraid of dust particles on earth, or a... 2

? How is this possible? Wouldn't we need other conditi... 2

Don't breath this

There are already measurments an astronaut can take to av...

? Shouldn't their space suits be impervious against suc... 3

? **Does these techniques used in the pharmaceutica...** 2

? How does this apparatus work?

Fig 2. “Conversation” topics in Perusall based on content in Fig 1.

Fig 3. Example of a single conversation within the paper. The initials refer to students and timestamps are provided for when the comments occurred.

1.2 Feedbackr

Feedbackr is a digital student response tool that can be used for immediate feedback in the classroom. It is a web-based tool which collects feedback anonymously. Questions consisting of text, equations, computer code, or figures can be sent directly to the students. The students then respond, and the feedback data is immediately sent back to the instructor. The main reasons for using Feedbackr in the Particle Technology courses were to (i) engage students and initiate discussion, (ii) identify “weak spots” in the student’s perception of a certain topic, and (iii) identify topics that need further discussion. Fig 4 is an example of a (figure) question that was administered to the class.

1.3 TeachCenter

TeachCenter is an online resource management tool for students to use for a particular course. It is similar to *Moodle*, in that it serves as a “hub” for course content and online student engagement for a particular course. However, also non-*Moodle*-based resources were hosted on TeachCenter: most important, links to etherpads were provided that acted as “virtual blackboards” for (i) feedback collection, and (ii) group formation. Also, a database of multiple-choice and calculation-based questions, which can be used for formative assessments, were hosted on TeachCenter. Since such applications of a *Moodle*-like environment are fairly standard nowadays, details related to TeachCenter are not further elaborated below.

Which statements are correct about the figure below:

- ...this is a typical result of a traditional cyclone design calculation.
- ...this is a typical result of a LES-based flow simulation used to design cyclones.
- ...this is a typical results of a 4-way coupled multiphase flow simulation that can be used to design cyclones.
- ...this is a typical result of a modern cyclone design calculation

Fig 4. Example of a Feedbackr question used in the Particle Technology courses.

The depth of a simple sedimentation chamber has to be determined based on...

<input type="checkbox"/> ...the device used for removing the particles, and consequently based on the particle concentration of the suspension.	21.7%	#5
<input type="checkbox"/> ...the total mass flow rate of the incoming suspension, independent of the width of the device.	8.7%	#2
<input type="checkbox"/> ...the total mass flow rate of the incoming suspension, and depending on the width of the device, as well as the viscosity of the incoming fluid.	65.2%	#15
<input type="checkbox"/> ...the sedimentation velocity of the suspended particles	17.4%	#4

Voted: 23 Show results immediately Multiple Choice Runtime: 5 hours 5 minutes 27 seconds

The design of sedimentation chambers for liquid-particle (LP) separations is ...

<input type="radio"/> ...easier than that for gas-particle systems, because mass-loadings are typically lower in LP separation	33.3%	#7
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Simple Sedimentation Equipment

You have to design the depth of a simple rectangular sedimentation device for a volumetric flow rate of 20 [m³/h]. The width of the device is fixed with 4 [m], the liquid viscosity is 1e-6 [m²/s], and the critical Reynolds number (defined by the mean flow speed and the hydraulic diameter) is 2000. What is the required minimum depth of the sedimentation device?

<input type="radio"/> 0.2 [m]	13.0%
<input type="radio"/> 1.15 [m]	21.7%

With Feedbackr

Fig 5. Example of a Feedbackr response session.

3. Preliminary Results

Since this was the first time Perusall was introduced in these courses, the instructors were in the preliminary stages of collecting data on how the readings enhanced student learning. In order to help encourage students to do the readings, extra-credit questions based on the readings were included in the final exam. Students who were annotating the assigned papers using Perusall were able to answer the extra-credit questions. Informal feedback from students inferred that they felt the readings complementing the course materials. One approach that was used to measure student engagement was to study “heat maps” of student activity. Specifically, these maps were used to measure the students’ activity and time used to read the papers. Fig 6 is an example of a “heat map” of student activity for one of the papers assigned.

Fig 6. Example of a heat map of student activity in Perusall

For the use of Feedbackr, the participation in the lecture classes fluctuated on a moderate level. Based on a Feedback questions, it was found that 19-25 students participated in these questionnaires, thus indicating that 38-50% of the students participate in the lecture units. This is significantly above average participation in previous editions of the particle technology sequence of lectures that did not use these digital tools.

4. Conclusions

Perusall, Feedbackr, and TeachCenter were used for the first time as digital tools to engage students in the Particle Technology course material, and to enhance their learning and understanding of core topics. In this “concept paper”, the authors describe the various digital tools employed in these courses. Although thorough assessment of student learning and engagement was not obtainable for the initial implementation, the authors concluded that a significant step to enhance student learning was achieved by attempting to use all three digital tools. The authors recommend that other instructors consider adopting one or more of these digital tools as a way to engage students both inside, and outside the classroom.

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